

Experimental Demonstration of an FPGA-based Outdoor VLC Broadcasting System

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Abstract—Visible light communication (VLC) uses light-emitting diodes (LEDs) to transmit data by turning them on and off at very high speeds, too fast for the human eye to perceive. In outdoor environments, LED-based streetlights can be utilized as VLC transmitters. Given the ubiquity of street lights, they are particularly useful for outdoor broadcasting as required in public safety systems. In this paper, we develop an FPGA-based VLC system with on-off keying using a LED-based streetlight. The system is built upon the Eclipse Z7 FPGA platform integrated with opto-electronic transmitter and receiver front-ends. We present error rate performance results up to transmission distances of 8 meters.

Index Terms—Visible light communication, FPGA implementation, optical wireless communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Visible Light Communication (VLC) is a wireless communication technology that uses visible portion of the electromagnetic spectrum (i.e., wavelengths of 380-750 nm) to transmit information [1]. The idea behind VLC is to use light-emitting diodes (LEDs) to transmit data by turning them on and off at very high speeds, too fast for the human eye to perceive. These changes in light intensity can then be detected by a receiver, such as a photodiode, and decoded to extract the transmitted information. VLC has been extensively studied for indoor use cases [2] and later applied to outdoor environments [3]. In particular, VLC has been studied for vehicular applications where headlights and taillights are used for data exchange among vehicles.

In outdoor environments, LED-based streetlights can be further utilized as VLC transmitters. Given the ubiquity of street lights, they are particularly useful for outdoor broadcasting as required in public safety systems. They can also serve as wireless hot spots for pedestrians and passing vehicles. Outdoor lights with specific illumination requirements have radiation patterns which obviously differ from their indoor counterparts. In particular, LED luminaires for road lighting are designed to minimize light pollution, increase comfort and visibility for drivers and pedestrians, and maximize efficiency

by directing light to the appropriate area of the road. Under such design constraints, their radiation patterns differ from their indoor counterparts. Based on non-sequential ray tracing simulations, Eldeeb *et al.* considers two-lane highway roads with light poles on both sides and uniformly separated from each other [4]. In order to analyze streetlight-based VLC transmission, they derive a closed-form expression for the probability distribution function for the path loss. In [5], relay-assisted handover is proposed for vehicular visible light communication networks where streetlights are regarded as access points. Bette *et al.* present a study of outdoor VLC communication scenarios that evaluates the performance of a streetlight VLC system. The study incorporates the realistic radiation pattern of a streetlamp in the simulation studies to obtain accurate estimates of the system performance [6].

In addition to the theoretical and simulation studies for outdoor VLC systems, some experimental studies were carried out. For example, to transmit identification codes for LED streetlights to cameras equipped with cameras, Trong *et al.* use an LED streetlight and two rolling shutters CMOS sensors by installing the experimental setup in an office environment [7]. A significant impact of energy efficiency in lighting applications is the reduction of energy consumption. Depending on actual needs, street light brightness can be dimmed. In addition, different lighting classes can be activated based on street activity. In [8], Knobloch analyzed the simulation model and conducted an experiment with appropriate improvements in channel gain to properly street lighting while it supports VLC [8]. He further investigated the effect of dimming and aperture on VLC performance [9]. In [10], another outdoor VLC experiment was carried out and data transmission up to 240 cm was demonstrated under different light intensities.

Most of the existing experimental works in the literature depend on laboratory equipment and offline signal processing. In this paper, we develop an FPGA-based VLC system with on-off keying (OOK) using a LED-based streetlight. For this purpose, we use Eclipse Z7 [11] platform which features analog-to-digital (ADC) and digital-to-analog (DAC) extension boards. At the transmitter, the processing system (PS) part of the FPGA consists of User Data Protocol (UDP) server where the packets are fed from external network. As soon as a packet arrives, it transfers that packet to processing logic (PL) part of the FPGA through AXI bus between PL and PS parts. The PL modulates the signal and feeds the LED driver. After

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Fig. 1. Overall system architecture.

the transmitted signal goes through the propagation medium, it is collected by a photodetector. A narrow band optical filter is used to prevent saturation and reduce environmental light noise. The analog output signal from photodetector is digitalized using ADC and fed to the demodulation block in the FPGA. Finally, the received package is transferred to a previously defined IP address through Ethernet.

The remainder of this paper is as follows. In Section II, we present the overall system architecture. In Section III, we discuss implementation issues on FPGA transmitter and receiver blocks. In Section IV, we provide our performance measurement results. Finally, we conclude in Section V.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 presents the overall system architecture. The system is built upon the Eclipse Z7 FPGA platform. It is implemented using C and VHDL languages on the Eclipse Z7 platform, which has a Xilinx Zynq-7010 SOC FPGA. C programming language is used on the PS side, and VHDL programming language is used on the PL side. The PL part of the FPGA typically handles signal modulation and demodulation, which are time-critical and processing-intensive steps. The PS part provides packet forwarding and Ethernet communication of the VLC system with external networks. UDP packets are created with Python software on the transmitter laptop and are transferred to the transmitter FPGA via an Ethernet cable. We have a front-end (including a photodetector and a trans-impedance amplifier) that interfaces with the FPGA. The output of the receiver front-end is an analog signal which feeds to the ADC (Analog Digital Converter) with an SMA cable.

The frame structure is illustrated in Fig. 2. Each frame has a header, a length of information, and a footer. Frame detection is based on the header and footer. At the receiver side, the photodetector output is transferred to the FPGA. The FPGA first demodulates the first bit of the header. When it demodulates the first bit correctly, it demodulates the second and third bits. When the demodulator correctly decodes the first three bits, it decodes the entire payload until the footer arrives. When the entire payload is demodulated, PS transfers the payload to the receiver laptop via an Ethernet cable.

Fig. 2. Frame structure.

III. FPGA TRANSMITTER AND RECEIVER IMPLEMENTATION

Fig. 3 shows the inner blocks of transmitter FPGA. The Software Development Kit (SDK) is the Integrated Design Environment (IDE) for creating embedded applications on Zynq APSoC. The implementation of the SDK is done using C language. The AXI General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) core provides a general-purpose input/output interface between PS and PL. SDK buffers incoming UDP packets to PL through AXI GPIO. The AXI GPIO uses the Xil_Out32 command and writes UDP packets to Block RAM (BRAM). The AXI GPIO uses BRAM to transmit UDP packets to the PL part. The Xil_Out32 command writes data to BRAM each with a length of 32 bit. The data also includes the length information. The PS writes UDP packets to BRAM at the address 0x40000000. After writing UDP packets to BRAM, the AXI GPIO sends an interrupt signal from the PS to PL. The PL detects the signal, and the modulator starts. The output signal of the modulator is transferred to the DAC Core. The input of this block is 1 bit, and the output is 14 bits. For the DAC input, it converts from 1 to 8100 (decimal) and 0 to 100 (decimal), so it gets a square wave with high-level 8100 and low-level 100. These signals are fed to the DAC.

Fig. 4 shows the inner blocks of receiver FPGA. The Demodulator in the PL block contains four separate blocks. These are Data Shift, Slide Window, Threshold, and BRAM blocks. The signal from the ADC enters the ADC Core as 16 bits. ADC Core transfers 16 bits to the Data Shift block. Shift operations are accomplished with multiplication and division by powers of two. Shifting the bits to the left does the multiplication, and shifting the bits to the right does the division. The Data Shift Block decreases the amplitude of the incoming signal. The analog signal amplitude is reduced by 4

Fig. 3. Inner blocks of transmitter FPGA.

Fig. 4. Inner blocks of receiver FPGA.

Fig. 5. Block diagram of experimental setup.

times to make the calculations in the Threshold block easier. This module clears 2 bits by shifting the data 2 bits to the right. The output of this block is still 16 bits. The Sliding Window block sends each received 16-bit data to 10 shift registers. The outputs of each register are then summed. As a result of this sum, the output of this module turns into a triangle, the highest value being 8100×10 and the minimum being 100×10 . The threshold value for the detection of 1s and 0s is then determined by the threshold block. The outputs of the Threshold block are transferred to BRAM. BRAM consists of two state machines. The first state machine adds the bits received from the threshold block to the bytes. Then, it saves them in temporary memory until the footer bytes are received. Then it creates a flag to start the following state machine. This state machine writes the data saved in the temporary memory to BRAM for subsequent reading by the PS side. SDK buffers incoming UDP data to the receiver PC via Ethernet.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

Fig. 5 illustrates the end-to-end block diagram of our experimental setup. The laptop with Python software generates the digital signal as the UDP packets at the transmitter side. Then,

Fig. 6. Experimental setup during measurements.

these UDP packets are transferred to the Eclipse Z7 FPGA with Zmod 1411 daughterboard through an ethernet cable. The transmitter front-end includes a high-power LED driver and an off-the-shelf street light. The Pelsan MADRID [12] lamps were used in our set-up. It consists of 36 LED chips. Each chip radiates 0.54 W with a full angle of half power of 110.4° . At the receiver front-end, an avalanche photodetector (APD) (Thorlabs APD130A/M [13]) collects optical signal and produces a photocurrent. The output analog signal from the photodetector is read by the ADC and transmitted digitally to the FPGA.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we experimentally evaluated the performance of an outdoor VLC system based on FPGA implementation. The experimental setup was built on the Eclipse Z7 FPGA with DAC and ADC expansion boards and a high-power LED driver. A commercial off the shelf street was used as the VLC transmitter. The 3 dB-bandwidth of the optoelectronic front-end (i.e., that consists of the streetlight and driver) was measured as 495 kHz which should be sufficient for broadcasting messages for public safety applications. Our BER measurements show that the system achieves a $P_e = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}$ at a distance of 6.5 m.

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Fig. 7. Bit error rate results.

First, we measured the bandwidth of the streetlight. For this purpose, we generated a wide frequency range signal from the signal generator and analyzed the resulting signal with APD in the spectrum analyzer. The 3 dB bandwidth of the street light was measured as 495 kHz which should be sufficient for broadcasting messages in public safety applications.

In Fig.7, we present the error rate performance of our VLC system set-up. The experiments are conducted for distances from $d = 0.5$ m up to $d = 9$ m with 0.5 m intervals. For each point, the transmitted frames were collected through the Wireshark software, and the error rate was computed from the received frames afterward. In the first test scenario where there is perfect alignment between transmitter and receiver, errors were first observed at $d = 6.5$ m, and a bit error rate (BER) of $P_e = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}$ was recorded. Shifting the receiver front end by 1 meter resulted in worse BER performance of $P_e = 1.3 \times 10^{-1}$ at the same propagation distance of 6.5 m. Similarly, while zero BER is recorded experimentally for line-of-sight (LOS) link up to the distance of 6 m, we observe $P_e = 8.0 \times 10^{-5}$ in the case of lateral shift. As the distance between the transmitter and receiver is increased to 8 meters, the transmission is stopped and no packets are received after this distance.